

Fungal Candidiasis and Its Role in Superficial and Systemic Infections

Sarah Omran Rasheed ✉

Ministry of Education, Salah al-Din Education Directorate, Tikrit Education Department, Iraq

Abstract

External parts of the body such as the skin, hair and nails are susceptible to infections caused by this yeast because it possesses two types of enzymes: protease and keratinase. These enzymes facilitate the yeast's ability to infect the keratinised outer layer. The incidence of fungal infections has increased in recent years due to increasing resistance to antifungal agents and the limited availability of antifungal treatments, which are often associated with numerous side effects.

Yeasts belong to important genera classified in the phylum Deuteromycotina (Imperfect Fungi). They are single-celled, eukaryotic organisms that reproduce asexually by budding. They lack a sexual phase and have oval cells with a diameter of 3 to 6 micrometres. Yeasts can occur as single cells or form pseudohyphae in host tissues where they develop germ tubes - a precursor to invasion of host tissues.

Colonies are smooth, soft, white to yellowish in colour and often give off a yeasty odour. Due to the absence of chlorophyll, yeasts exhibit nutritional heterogeneity and dimorphism, allowing them to grow in either hyphal or yeast form depending on environmental conditions.

The species *Candida albicans* is one of the most important pathogenic yeasts responsible for candidiasis, a fungal infection that can be primary or secondary and is caused by different species within the genus *Candida*. The infection can be acute, subacute or chronic, causing localised lesions in the mouth, throat, skin, vagina, fingers, nails and trachea. In some cases, the infection can spread systemically, affecting the lungs and gastrointestinal tract (Dignani et al, 2009).

Keywords: *Candidiasis, C. albicans, Mannoprotein, Germ Tube, Superficial Infection, Phenotypic Switching.*

Suggested citation: Rasheed, S.O. (2025). Fungal Candidiasis and Its Role in Superficial and Systemic Infections. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(2), 3-11. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(2).01

Introduction

Candida species can infect humans and can occur naturally as yeasts on the skin, in the lower genital tract of women, in the gastrointestinal tract and on mucous membranes. More than 150 species of *Candida* have been identified, with *C. albicans* being the most common and pathogenic in humans, followed by other clinically important species such as *C. pseudotropicalis*, *C. guilliermondii* and *C. tropicalis*.

These different species of *Candida* share two important phenotypic characteristics. The first is their ability to form small, round yeast cells that reproduce by budding. These cells are typically oval, between 3 and 6 microns in size, and are identified as thick-walled large cells that originate from the tip of the pseudohyphae, which can also be a diagnostic feature. Pseudohyphae are a second important characteristic of these fungi, when they develop into elongated chains of interconnected yeast cells with distinct constrictions. Healthcare professionals consider the formation of pseudohyphae to be an

essential criterion for the diagnosis of *C. albicans*. The microorganism *Candida* species produces spores that appear together with true septate hyphae, which scientists have observed primarily in *C. tropicalis*.

Candida albicans can produce true hyphae when it encounters certain environmental situations or nutritional factors thus acting as an essential diagnostic indicator. When cultivated under aerobic conditions on a growth medium with a pH range between 2.5 and 7.5, at temperatures between 20°C and 38°C, *Candida* species form smooth, convex, milky colonies with a characteristic yeasty odour. The yeast cultures begin to grow between 48 to 72 hours after isolation (Webb *et al.*, 1998).

Most species in the genus *Candida* are generally similar and are characterised by budding cells that are gram-positive and form blastospores. These blastospores vary in shape from oval to elongated or circular. Notably, *C. albicans* has the ability to transition from budding oval yeast cells (blastospores) to the pseudohyphal form.

All pathogenic *Candida* species can metabolise and ferment glucose as a carbon source, but lack the ability to utilise nitrate as a nitrogen source. However, they vary in their ability to utilise other carbon and nitrogen sources. The ability to metabolise and ferment different carbon sources has been used to differentiate *Candida* species (Wiederhold, 2017).

The current study aimed to investigate *Candida* spp from infections in different parts of the body. The infection can be acute, moderate, subacute or chronic. The pathogen causes local infections in the mouth, throat, skin, vagina, fingers, nails and trachea, and it can spread within the body, infecting the lungs, gastrointestinal tract or systemic infections. Diagnosis is the first step in the treatment and prevention of *Candida* infections, as knowledge of the causative species facilitates the process of studying its virulence factors.

Classification of *Candida* spp.

Yeasts are important genera classified in the phylum Deuteromycotina (Imperfect Fungi). However, some strains have recently been reclassified within the Ascomycota due to their ability to form ascospore structures.

Kingdom: Fungi

Phylum: Ascomycota

Subphylum: Saccharomycotina

Class: Saccharomycetes

Order: Saccharomycetales

Family: Saccharomycetaceae

Genus: Candida

These organisms are eukaryotic and unicellular but can also form true hyphae and pseudohyphae. They reproduce asexually by fission, budding, and the formation of conidia. These yeasts lack a sexual phase and exhibit nutritional heterogeneity due to the absence of chlorophyll (Lumbsch & Huhndorf, 2007).

Cell Wall Structure of *Candida* spp.

The hyphal wall of *Candida* contains about three times more chitin than yeast cells. It is composed of mannoproteins, β -glucans and small amounts of chitin. The main component of the wall is carbohydrate, together with lipids and proteins. This composition extends to hyphae, germ tubes and yeast cells, but changes during morphological differentiation.

The cell wall serves as a critical site for yeast adhesion to target cells, enabling tissue colonisation. It also plays an important role in the secretion of virulence factors and acts as a target for antibodies and antifungal drugs designed to inhibit or kill fungal cells (Tumer & Ozturk,2021).

The difference in cell wall composition between the yeast and hyphal forms of *Candida* makes the latter more adhesive. The adhesion process between *Candida albicans* and epithelial cells is made possible by mannoprotein molecules. The cell wall is made up of several layers, derived from its proximity to the plasma membrane, starting with β -glucan, then mannoprotein, followed by fibrillar and finally chitin layers.

C. albicans has a fuzzy coat on its outer surface. The fibrillar layer actively assists in cell-cell binding interactions and resists phagocytic action. The outer cell wall receptors in *C. albicans* bind to polymorphonuclear leukocytes.

Fungal invasion, dissemination and adaptation occur when the fungi penetrate the skin or mucous membranes. In newborns, this can occur during passage through the birth canal of an infected mother, where *C. albicans* colonises the oral cavity and parts of the gastrointestinal tract (both upper and lower).

Yeast adapts to persist as a commensal organism within the normal flora of the body. However, it can become an opportunistic pathogen under conditions such as immune system dysfunction or physiological changes, including pregnancy, diabetes, cancer, prolonged antibiotic use or immunosuppressive treatments (Francois et al, 2013).

Pathogenesis of *Candida albicans*

The term candidiasis refers to fungal infections caused by species of the genus *Candida*. These infections may be acute, moderate or chronic and may be either superficial or invasive. Superficial infections typically affect the skin and mucous membranes, while invasive infections include isolation of *Candida* from the bloodstream and deep candidiasis.

These fungi can live in deep parts of the body, with deep candidiasis being very dangerous as it can lead to the death of the infected person. Many sources indicate that *C. albicans* is the main cause of candidiasis, followed by other species such as *C. tropicalis* and *C. glabrata* (Zemestani et al., 2016).

Clinical Manifestations of *Candida* Infections

There are more than 200 species of *Candida*, but only a few are capable of causing infections in humans, and these infections are rare. They typically occur when the host's immune system is weakened.

These infections are divided into:

- Superficial infections;
- Systemic infections.

First: Cutaneous Candidiasis

The areas between the skin folds are affected by *Candida* yeast and this infection is called intertriginous candidiasis. It commonly affects the armpits, under the breasts and between the thighs, as these areas provide a suitable environment for infection due to their moisture and warmth. The area between the fingers and toes is also susceptible, especially due to prolonged exposure to water, as in the case of cooks and housewives. The affected area becomes red, ulcerated and peels off, leaving a painful, exposed area. *Candida* yeast has also been shown to infect the area under and around the nail plate, a condition known as paronychia, which causes swelling and redness of the nail fold, accompanied by severe pain and accumulation of inflammatory secretions. Brown discolouration of the nails is a chronic result of this

type of infection. A particular infection develops in people who spend many hours in contact with water and in people diagnosed with diabetes (Perez-Sayans et al, 2021).

Second: Oral Candidiasis

The most common fungal infection of the oral cavity is oral candidiasis, which occurs in people with local immunosuppressive conditions. The characteristic symptom of the disease is the formation of white lesions over the tongue body and gum tissue, together with the tonsils and the inside of the cheeks. Young children commonly develop oral thrush after the infection is passed from an infected mother's vaginal canal to the baby during birth. It also affects older people. The development of *Candida* from a harmless to a pathogenic state occurs because of both oral hygiene problems and a weakened immune system. People with AIDS, cancer or any other disease-related immunocompromised condition often develop this disease (Patel et al, 2016).

Third: Vulvovaginal Candidiasis (VVC)

Research shows that vulvovaginal candidiasis (VVC) affects one million women worldwide each year. The main cause of this condition is *Candida albicans* infection, although other species cause it less frequently (Suchodolski & Krasowska, 2021). Chronic vaginal *Candida* infection results in red lesions with white discharge that cause painful burning and itching in women who are pregnant, taking oral contraceptives, or of reproductive age. The condition occurs when antibiotics are used inappropriately or indiscriminately. Pregnant women need to be cautious when treating vulvovaginal candidiasis, as such treatment may cause problems for the foetus. Vulvovaginal candidiasis in women can spread to their male sexual partners. *C. albicans* is the primary fungal species causing this condition, with *C. glabrata* as the secondary species (Yassin et al, 2020).

Second: Systemic Infections

Systemic infections spread through the heart to other organs in the body, including the brain, eyes, lungs, joints, liver and reproductive organs. Fungi in the bloodstream cause a condition known as fungemia, but they can also cause inflammation of the heart valves, known as endocarditis, and inflammation of the brain, known as meningitis. The course of the disease varies depending on where the fungal infection occurs (Monia et al, 2014).

Mechanism of Candidiasis and Virulence Factors

The human body contains pathogenic yeasts known as *Candida*, with the genus *Candida* being one of the most commonly encountered groups due to its strong infectious capabilities. The gastrointestinal tract, together with the oral, urinary and reproductive tracts, are the main sites where endogenous infections with this pathogenic yeast occur. Many common *Candida* species infect the urinary and genital tracts, causing infections in these areas and sometimes entering the bloodstream. *Candida* species are rarely found in environmental sources such as soil and water. They are dimorphic organisms, capable of changing shape depending on the environment. *Candida* can also survive at 37°C, the human body temperature.

Candida species grow at temperatures between 20-40°C and a pH range of 3-8. These yeasts are considered part of the normal flora in the body, but are usually unable to cause infection due to the presence of *Lactobacillus* bacteria which inhibit their growth. However, under certain conditions, such as a weakened immune system or diseases that impair immune function, *Candida* can become a pathogenic organism and cause superficial, subcutaneous and systemic infections. *Candida* is an opportunistic fungus that causes infection when the immune system is compromised. Colonies growing on specialised fungal media, such as Sabouraud dextrose agar, appear soft, cream-coloured, convex and

have a yeast-like odour. Older colonies are larger and have irregular, rough edges (Upadhyay & Pandey, 2019).

Mechanism of Infection

The process of infection involves the following steps: Fungal infection is defined as the entry of pathogenic fungi into the tissues of the body, followed by their multiplication within the body. The infection may be asymptomatic or may become clinically evident due to the release of toxic metabolic by-products, fungal proliferation or the immune response of the infected individual.

The mechanisms involved include

1. The ability of Candida species to withstand high temperatures up to 37°C, the normal human body temperature, as seen in *C. albicans*. *C. albicans* and other species of the same genus are part of the natural microbiota (normal flora) as they coexist as commensal organisms on the human skin and are found in the mouth, gastrointestinal tract and vagina. They maintain a balanced relationship with other microbiota present in the body. As an opportunistic microorganism, *C. albicans* can become a pathogenic organism under certain conditions. These conditions include excessive and indiscriminate use of broad-spectrum antibiotics without medical advice, diabetes, infection with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), and in people whose immune systems have been weakened by chemotherapy, radiotherapy for cancer, or the use of immunosuppressive drugs, such as in organ transplant recipients. In these cases, the source of infection is endogenous. However, the infection can also be exogenous when artificial components such as prosthetic heart valves, prosthetic joints or catheters used in veins, arteries or the urinary tract are implanted in the human body (Yang & Lin, 2021).

2. Ability to Produce Endotoxins (Candidotoxin)

Candida species have the ability to produce endotoxins, also known as candidotoxin, due to their ability to produce hydrolytic enzymes such as proteinase. This enzyme can break down immunoglobulins (antibodies). Other enzymes include phospholipase and keratinase, which also contribute to the pathogenicity of Candida (Baron et al, 1990).

3. Adherence Ability

The ability of Candida to adhere to epithelial cells in the oral cavity, vaginal tract and gastrointestinal tract is one of the first steps in the pathogenesis of infection. The greater the ability of the pathogen to adhere, the faster the infection progresses, especially if the organism is commensal with the host, such as Candida. In this case, it becomes more able to adhere to host cells, such as the epithelial cells that line the oral cavity, urogenital system and other mucosal tissues. The sugar compounds galactosamine, mannosamine, amino sugars and glucosamine in certain concentrations have a strong blocking effect on the adherence process. Scientists have found that Candida's adhesive protein, mannoprotein, binds to specific receptors on host epithelial cells. The pathogen cells require specific surface elements to bind to target cell components in order to establish adherence. This adherence process is both promoted and inhibited by a number of factors, including the structure and amount of sugars, as well as temperature and pH conditions.

The hydrophobic nature of Candida, combined with its inability to affinity for fluids, provides one of the strongest forces maintaining yeast-epithelial cell binding after attachment. The interaction of yeast with normal flora bacteria and yeast populations has two effects on adherence intensity at body sites, including the gut and vagina, based on the response of these microbes to yeast. Adherence is supported by two yeast characteristics: its compatibility with epithelial cells lining body tissues and its ability to modify surface properties. The ability of yeast cells to adhere to epithelial cells depends on physical conditions such as pH and temperature, with cells maintained at 25°C showing better adherence than cells cultured

at 37°C. Adherence shows both enhancement and inhibition responses to the pH range identified by research (Costa et al., 2012).

4. Germ Tube Production

The pathogenicity of *C. albicans* is largely dependent on its virulence factor, the ability to form germ tubes. Direct effects on adhesion processes result from the germ tube structure. The surface of yeast cells contains alpha-beta5 and alpha-beta3 receptors in addition to germ tube structures in most *C. albicans* strains, as reported by Spreghini et al. (1999). Binding of these receptors to the compound vitronectin allows epithelial cells to adhere through the receptor binding process, leading to potential infection.

A germ tube is a fibrous part that develops from yeast cell walls or blastospores and extends outwards to form a branched, elongated structure. The germ tube is essential for infection and is used by medical professionals to characterise how dangerous a strain is to human health. Germ tube development functions as a vital pathogenic element in Candida infections, as this mechanism helps Candida to invade host tissue while maintaining resistance to phagocytosis. The identification of germ tubes in tissue studies or pathological models is evidence of tissue invasion, making the detection of these elements essential for diagnosis (Collee et al, 1996).

Bacteria develop germ tubes when grown at temperatures between 35°C and 37°C under specific experimental conditions. The stimulation of germ tube production is highly dependent on the precise choice of culture medium used for the experiment. The most successful agents for stimulating germ tube formation include plasma and egg albumin, together with bone marrow fluid and seminal fluid. Germ tube formation is stimulated by two specialised media types which include human serum combined with egg albumin. The ability to form germ tubes is unique to *C. albicans* among Candida species, making this the primary mechanism of infection in Candida. The germ tube-positive Candida strains belong to a single *C. albicans* category because any Candida species showing germ tube production is directly identified as *C. albicans*.

Figure 1. The Figure Illustrates Budding, Germ Tube Formation, and Chlamydospore Formation in *C. albicans* yeast.

Other Candida species fall into the germ tube negative category because they lack this characteristic and do not produce a germ tube. The germ tube-producing strain belongs to *C. dubliniensis*, although its tube is different from that produced by *C. albicans*. The researchers identified this species in the mouth when it caused oral thrush before finding other clinical samples, including urine and vaginal discharge, and sputum and stool from both HIV-positive and HIV-negative patients.

The taxonomic groups of *C. albicans* and *C. dubliniensis* show contrasting forms of classification. The growth of *C. dubliniensis* strains is limited at 45°C and, unlike *C. albicans*, they lack the ability to metabolise trehalose, D-xylose and x-methyl-D-glucoside.

Several factors can inhibit germ tube formation, including a reduced iron ion concentration in the medium. Additionally, short-term exposure to specific antifungal drugs at certain concentrations can alter the speed of germ tube formation and modify the receptors on the yeast cell surface, which in turn inhibits adherence and prevents infection (Bhavan *et al.*, 2010).

5. Phenotypic Switching

Candida yeast is characterised by its ability to undergo phenotypic switching in colonies growing on different solid media, including a change in colony colour from pale white to dark and transformation into small colonies (petite). In addition, the yeast is capable of forming a filamentous form when it switches from the yeast form to the filamentous form when attacking host tissues. Both true and pseudohyphae can be involved in the pathogenicity of different Candida species. The appearance of disease symptoms is associated with the presence of true hyphae. Many studies have confirmed that the filamentous form is more effective in causing disease (Koneman *et al.*, 1992).

Candida is found in the gut as yeast (spores) when non-pathogenic, but when it infects the skin or mucous membranes it transforms into a filamentous mycelial form that can be seen under the microscope in skin samples, as well as the formation of chlamydospores, which are characterised by their thick walls. This occurs when cultured on nutrient-poor media such as Corn Meal Agar (CMA), resulting in the production of resistant chlamydospores. Both Walsh & Dixon (1991) suggest that the dimorphism of Candida is due to its transformation from the blastospore form to the filamentous form via an intermediate structure known as the germ tube. These spores, together with the germ tube, are important diagnostic features for *C. albicans*, the yeast responsible for 92% of Candida infections.

6. Production of Hydrolytic Enzymes

Enzymes are one of the virulence factors that complement the pathogenicity of Candida. One of the most important enzymes produced by these yeasts are protein-digesting enzymes (proteinases). The yeast *C. albicans* is able to secrete aspartyl proteinase, which breaks down proteins and accelerates the penetration of yeast cells into host tissues, allowing them to establish an infection. Both *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis* are highly capable of degrading and killing cells. In addition, *C. albicans* secretes protein-digesting enzymes in media containing albumin as a nitrogen source, particularly at low pH.

Phospholipase enzymes (types A, B, C) are also important virulence factors in Candida species. These enzymes help to adhere to and damage host epithelial cells in the early stages of host invasion and facilitate germ tube penetration into tissues by concentrating at the tip of the fungal hyphae. In addition, Candida yeasts produce a haemolytic factor (haemolysin) that breaks down red blood cells to release haemoglobin as a source of iron, an essential nutrient for yeast growth in the host (Suchodolski & Krasowska, 2021).

Conclusions

Age has a close relationship with candidiasis, especially in women of fertile age, marriage or pregnancy. As for newborn children, they are most likely to be infected by their infected mothers. Candida susceptibility and resistance depend on several factors, including (the concentration of the antifungal, the surrounding environment, its location in the organism's body, as well as the weakness of the infected person's immune system). The pathogenic nature of *C. albicans* depends significantly on its virulence factor, which is its ability to develop germ tubes. Direct effects on adhesion processes result from the germ tube structure. The ability of Candida species to withstand high temperatures up to 37°C, which is the normal human body temperature. Candida species have the ability to produce endotoxins, also known as

candidotoxin, due to their ability to produce hydrolytic enzymes such as proteinase. The ability of *Candida* to adhere to epithelial cells in the oral cavity, vaginal tract and gastrointestinal tract is one of the first steps in the pathogenesis of infection. *Candida* yeast is characterised by its ability to undergo phenotypic switching in colonies growing on different solid media, including a change in colony colour from pale white to dark and transformation into small colonies. Enzymes are among the virulence factors that complement the pathogenicity of *Candida*. One of the most important enzymes produced by these yeasts is proteinase, a protein-digesting enzyme.

References

- Baron, E. J., Chang, R. S., Howard, D. H., Miller, J. N., & Turner, J. A. (1994). *Medical Microbiology: A Short Course* (4-е изд.). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Bhavan, P. S., Rajkumar, R., Radhakrishnan, S., Seenivasan, C., & Kannan, S. (2010). Culture and identification of *Candida albicans* from vaginal ulcer and separation of enolase on SDS-PAGE. *International Journal of Biology*, 2(1), 84–93. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijb.v2n1p84>
- Colle, J. G., Fraser, A. G., Marmion, B. P., & Simmons, A. (1996). *Practical Medical Microbiology* (4-е изд., Т. 1). Churchill Livingstone.
- Costa, A. C., Campos Rasteiro, V. M., da Silva Hashimoto, E. S., Araújo, C. F., Pereira, C. A., Junqueira, J. C., & Jorge, A. O. (2012). Effect of erythrosine- and LED-mediated photodynamic therapy on buccal candidiasis infection of immunosuppressed mice and *Candida albicans* adherence to buccal epithelial cells. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology, Oral Radiology*, 114(4), 67–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oooo.2012.02.014>
- Dignani, M. C., Solomkin, J. S., & Anaissie, E. J. (2009). *Candida*. B. E. J. Anaissie, M. R. McGinnis, & M. A. Pfaller (Реда.), *Clinical Mycology* (2-е изд., стр. 197–229). Churchill Livingstone.
- François, L. M., Duncan, W., & Bernhard, H. (2013). *Candida albicans* pathogenicity mechanisms. *Fungal Genetics and Biology*, 4(2), 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fgb.2013.01.005>
- Koneman, E. W., Allen, S. D., Janda, W. M. J., Schreckenber, P. C., & Winn, W. C. (1992). *Diagnostic Microbiology* (4-е изд.). J. B. Lippincott Company.
- Lumbsch, H. T., & Huhndorf, S. M. (2007). Myconet Volume 14. Part One. Outline of Ascomycota—2009. Part Two. Notes on Ascomycete Systematics. Nos. 4751–5113. *Fieldiana Life and Earth Sciences*, 2010(1), 1–64. <https://doi.org/10.3158/1557-4542-12.1.1>
- Ouederni, M., Sanal, O., Ikinciogullari, A., Tezcan, I., Dogum, F., Sologuren, I., Pedraza-Sánchez, S., Keser, M., Tanir, G., & Nieuwhof, C. (2014). Clinical features of candidiasis in patients with inherited interleukin 12 receptor β 1 deficiency. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 58(2), 204–213. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cit703>
- Patel, H. K., Patel, P. H., & Nerurkar, A. B. (2016). A study of superficial mycoses with its clinical correlation at GMERS Medical College and Hospital Valsad, Gujarat. *Indian Journal of Microbiology Research*, 3(1), 69–73. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2394-5478.2016.00016.1>
- Pérez-Sayáns, M., Beiro-Fuentes, R., Otero-Rey, E. M., Chamorro-Petronacci, C. M., Gándara-Vila, P., Somoza-Martín, J. M., & Blanco-Carrión, A. (2021). Efficacy of different formulations of nystatin in an experimental model of oral candidiasis in sialoadenectomized rats. *Journal of Dental Sciences*, 16(1), 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jds.2020.06.010>

- Spreghini, E., Gismondi, A., Piccoli, M., & Sontoni, G. (1999). Evidence for $\alpha\beta 3$ and $\alpha\beta 5$ integrin-like vitronectin (VN) receptors in *Candida albicans* and their involvement in yeast cell adhesion to VN. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 180(1), 156–166. <https://doi.org/10.1086/314842>
- Suchodolski, J., & Krasowska, A. (2021). Fructose induces fluconazole resistance in *Candida albicans* through activation of Mdr1 and Cdr1 transporters. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(4), 2127. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22042127>
- Tumer, S., Bayraktar, M., & Öztürk, A. (2021). Distribution of clinical *Candida* species and their susceptibility to antifungal agents. *Reviews in Medical Microbiology*, 32(3), 169–174. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MRM.0000000000000240>
- Upadhyay, V., Kumar, A., Singh, A. K., & Pandey, J. (2019). Epidemiological characterization of dermatophytes at a tertiary care hospital in Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. *Current Medical Mycology*, 5(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.18502/cmm.5.1.7>
- Walsh, T. J., & Dixon, D. M. (1991). Spectrum of mycoses. B S. M. Barone & P. M. Jenning (PeA), *Medical Microbiology* (3-е изд.). Wiley.
- Webb, B. C., Thomas, C. J., Willcox, M. D. P., Harty, D. W. S., & Knox, K. W. (1998). *Candida*-associated denture stomatitis: Aetiology and management: A review. Part 1. Factors influencing the distribution of *Candida* species in the oral cavity. *Australian Dental Journal*, 43(1), 45–50. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1834-7819.1998.tb00152.x>
- Wiederhold, N. P. (2017). Antifungal resistance: Current trends and future strategies to combat. *Infection and Drug Resistance*, 10, 249–259. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S124918>
- Yang, Y., Lin, L., Li, Y., Jiang, Z., Li, C., Liu, M., & Lin, X. (2021). Etiology, microbiological isolates, and antibiotic susceptibilities in culture-proven pediatric endophthalmitis: A 9-year review. *Graefes' Archive for Clinical and Experimental Ophthalmology*, 259(1), 197–204. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00417-020-04920-0>
- Yassin, M. T., Mostafa, A. A. F., & Al-Askar, A. A. (2020). In vitro anticandidal potency of *Syzygium aromaticum* (clove) extracts against vaginal candidiasis. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*, 20(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-020-2831-0>
- Zemestani, M., Rafrat, M., & Asghari-Jafarabadi, M. (2016). Chamomile tea improves glycemic indices and antioxidants status in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nutrition*, 32(1), 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2015.07.011>

